

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10471769>

Abstract. *In the field of medicine, terms have considerable role. Considering that the main part of the terms of this area came from Latin and English, it turns out how important it is to teach English in medical universities. This article will conduct a review of these issues.*

Keywords: *medicine, term, translation, English, method, teaching.*

INTRODUCTION

The need to revise some aspects of teaching English to medical university students is increasing day by day. It is determined only by the fact that the comprehensive development of competencies that ensure high-quality communication of future doctors with foreign counterparts in various academic and professional situations is the main important factor in the effectiveness and scope of work of medical personnel of our country.

MAIN PART

In fact, there are some difficulties and problems in teaching a foreign language in non-philological higher education institutions. First of all, this is the fact that the preparation time can be severely limited. Secondly, the specific requirements and needs of students present additional difficulties for the teacher, which is associated with the implementation of English in the field of highly specialized professional communication. Taking into account the insufficient level of General English skills of students, mastering medical terminology is considered quite laborious. Because it is necessary that the student, even in one lesson, master the terms of the topic, be able to compose a sentence for grammatical devices, freely use the given reading and listening comprehension exercises. The periodized stages of each process, from the specific simple to the complex, facilitate the level of mastering.

But even an experienced ESP teacher may sometimes, with the help of pedagogical tactics or a curriculum, not achieve the desired result. In this, the students themselves, the content determines which method is effective. For example, in the early 1980s, Chinese English practice was organized in the same way. This used techniques such as “intensive reading”, a detailed reading exercise, and a word - for-word approach over the text. In the case of South African universities, skills such as reading, writing and critical thinking have also been formulated.

We analyze the methods of semanticizing medical terms, describe the principles of planning an English lesson for medical students, and suggest methods for developing dialogical speech skills at different stages of the lesson. We will consider and group the most effective methods of teaching language aspects, use them in written and oral speech; provide criteria for the selection of educational materials aimed at the formation and improvement, development of phonetic, lexical, grammatical, morphological and syntactic abilities. Listening is a mandatory component of any English language as a foreign language lesson. We present possible topics and options for working with anatomical and clinical terminology. In place of the conclusion, the teaching of the specialty language for students of the faculty of medicine should be diverse,

multidisciplinary and include work on the implementation of three main goals: teaching, development and upbringing.

In a professional context, it is important for medical students to know and understand all the features of medical terminology in the methodology of teaching English for special purposes. Working with a professional vocabulary goes through the following stages: 1) presentation of a new vocabulary; 2) formation of lexical skills; 3) organization of conditions for reviewing new dictionaries [1].

Scientific and technical literature is characterized by the use of terminological units. Thousands of words and combinations of words belong to the terminological systems of science, technology, trade, law, sport. These language units are not used or even understood by people outside of a particular specialty. Any science or field of activity has a special vocabulary. There is a special medical dictionary and also special terminologies such as chemistry, physics, energy, economics, building construction, aviation and others. Teaching vocabulary is one of the priorities of teaching English for special purposes. The relevance of teaching a foreign language to a specialty is determined by the use of this language in professional activities and mastering communication skills on professional topics, as well as the need to read, abstract and translate special literature [2].

It is known that the teaching of the terminological dictionary as part of the science of a foreign language for special purposes is one of the most important parts of the tasks of forming professionally oriented communicative competence of non-philological students. Medical terminology is a specific terminology used to effectively and accurately achieve the goal of communication in the field of healthcare. Medical terminology has a number of distinctive features that differ from other term systems. Most medical words combined forms of Greek and Latin origin. This feature of word making can be used to help students use these words.

The teaching of Latin along with English in the medical direction helps them to remember that some medical terms are written the same in every 2 languages, pronounced [3]:

<i>English</i>	<i>Latin</i>	<i>Uzbek</i>
esophagus	eosphagus	qizilo'ngach
appendix	appendice	appenditsit
cecum	cecum	ko'richak
pharynx	pharynx	halqum
autopsia/ autopsy	autopsia	otopsiya, murdani yorish
lymphoma	lymphoma	limfoma
chylostasis	chylostasis	xilostaz
anaemia	anaemia	anemiya, kamqonlik
histology	histologia	gistologiya

When choosing educational methods, it is considered advisable to choose based on the didactic task of each lesson. Having gained the interest of students by the teacher, their activity in the educational process should be constantly stimulated. Today, the use of modern means of technology, information technology, computer science, multimedia, internet, distance learning, unified information environment and similar information and Communication technologies has paid off for the meaningful organization of the educational process in medical institutions.

Today, the study of the scientific and theoretical foundations of new innovative pedagogical technologies and their application in educational processes in medical universities leads to the achievement of high efficiency in the teaching process.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The use of innovative teaching methods will be of particular importance in the preparation of students in the conditions of the modern need of the labor market. Innovative methods teach students active methods of obtaining new knowledge, allow them to occupy the highest level of social FAO, strengthen the creative competence of even more students and help to bring the reading process closer to a daily life experience.

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